

Low-NA Two-photon lithography patterning of metal/dielectric tapered optical fibers for depth-selective, volumetric optical neural interfaces

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Abstract

Optical neural implants allow neuroscientists to access deep brain regions, enabling to decipher complex patterns of neural activity. In this field, the use of optical fibers is rapidly increasing, and the ability to generate high-quality metal patterns on their nonplanar surface would further extend their application. Here we propose to use alternating metal shielding and dielectric confinement to engineer the mode-division properties of tapered optical fiber neural implants. This is accomplished through an unconventional application of two-photon lithography (TPL), which employs a low-numerical aperture objective to pattern extensive waveguide sections at both low and high curvature radii. The low-NA TPL is used to polymerize a mask of photoresist, while the rest of the taper undergoes to wet metal etching. This implies no direct destructive interaction between the laser beam and the metal to be removed, preserving the optical properties of the dielectric waveguide and of the metal coating. The advantages provided by the presented fabrication method, combined with the intrinsic modal properties of the dielectric waveguide, enable the engineering of the light guiding mechanisms, achieving depth-selective light delivery with a high extinction ratio. The device's light emission and collection properties were investigated in quasi-transparent media and highly scattering brain slices, finding that our proposed method facilitates 360° symmetric light collection around the dielectric-confined section with depth resolution. This opens novel perspective for the realization of optical neural implants that can interface all-around the implant axis, with low-NA TPL that can be applied also on other types of non-planar surfaces.

Introduction

Understanding the complex organization of the brain is central to deciphering neural circuits and mapping the insurgence of dysfunction linked to brain disease. To this goal, optical methods [1][2] greatly support neuroscientists in understanding the fundamental mechanisms of communications among groups of neurons, and optical neural interfaces are nowadays a widely employed tool in neuroscience labs. However,

accessing the brain with light is challenging, due to high scattering and short photons mean free path [3]. Indeed, single photon microscopy is limited to imaging the shallower layers of the brain, and multiphoton microscopy struggles to access brain structures located deeper than 1.3 mm [4][5][6]. To explore deep brain regions, implantable devices are therefore necessary, aiming to establish a bi-directional optical channel with neurons to excite and collect functional fluorescence [7] [8]. Planar micro- and nano-fabrication techniques have been widely employed to conceive implantable shanks for deep-brain light delivery, including solid-state waveguides [9][10] and micro-light-emitting diodes [11]. They can be coupled to photodetectors and single-photon avalanche photodiodes, providing integrated light detection capabilities in free-moving mice [12][13]. An alternative approach involves developing technological platforms based on optical fibers. Both silica-based and polymeric waveguides are being investigated by the scientific community. Polymeric systems can be engineered to obtain soft implantable waveguides that can host several functions [14]. However, their intrinsic autofluorescence makes them less suitable for light collection. In contrast, silica-based multimode optical fibers, despite being stiffer, are less prone to autofluorescence and allow the exploitation of the waveguide's modal properties to both deliver light and collect the generated functional fluorescence [15], [16].

In this framework, tapered optical fibers (TFs) provide a method for establishing a bi-directional optical interaction between multiple subsets of guided modes and the surrounding neural tissue [15][18][19][20]. TFs are characterized by a narrowing section that extends for a few millimeters, ending with a $< 1\mu\text{m}$ tip which reduces tissue damage with respect to flat-cleaved implantable systems [19]. As the waveguide narrows, the number of guided modes decreases, enabling modal-selective interaction with the surrounding tissue. This sets communication channels that have been employed to both deliver and collect light from the entire depth of functional structures of the mouse brain [19], [21] and to exploit mode-division multiplexing/demultiplexing to obtain axial selective light delivery and collection. Mode-division along the taper can be controlled and engineered by (i) acting on the wavevector of the light injected into the waveguide and/or (ii) by micropatterning the taper edge to harness modal properties *in situ*. For (i), an angle-selective injection system can be used to excite only a subset of guided modes to obtain light delivery or collection from a specific taper section. Method (ii) requires the taper to be coated by a metal reflective layer, apart from specific portions (referred to as dielectric regions) at which a subset of the guided modes can exchange optical energy with the brain tissue [22][19][18]. This sets a hybrid metal-dielectric guiding mechanism whose control is challenging due to the need to microstructure a non-planar surface with a non-constant radius of curvature. Indeed, while the taper narrows, the radius of curvature ($R(y)$) decreases down to $< 1\mu\text{m}$ (**Figure 1A**). Therefore, the employed microfabrication method to achieve such hybrid guiding mechanism should feature a resolution comparable with $R(y)$, warranting also unaltered optical properties of the dielectric region as well as steep transitions between the metallic and dielectric regions, to exploit at best the modal properties of the waveguide. However, so far employed microfabrication methods are not completely efficient in this respect. Focus Ion Beam (FIB) milling enables sub-50 nm patterning resolution [23], but it usually employs high atomic weight ions (such as Ga^+) that locally increase the waveguide's refractive index due to ion implantation [24], especially when large dielectric region is to be uncovered. This reduces the efficiency of inward and outward photon transmission across the fiber-tissue interface and can perturb light propagation in the waveguide. In addition, no selectivity between the metal coating and the fused silica can be exploited during the FIB milling, generating a surface roughness in the order of a few fractions of visible light wavelengths [25]. An alternative approach to FIB milling is optical ablation (OA) of the metal layer via ultrafast laser pulses. Ultraviolet Direct Laser Writing (UV-DLW) has the advantage of faster fabrication time, but sub-micrometer features require high-numerical aperture (NA)

focusing and the consequent generation of local heating, altering the geometry of ablated spots and inducing surface roughness [26]. Near-Infrared Laser Writing (NIR-DLW) instead preserves better the TF's silica surface by employing a NIR femtosecond pulsed laser to ablate the metal coating while monitoring two-photon fluorescence signal simultaneously generated in the environment by the same fs laser pulses. However, in this case, the radiation is absorbed by the metal section, which is unable to dissipate energy inducing strong deformation of the patterns also for features above $>10\mu\text{m}$ [27]. Therefore, the main limitations of such methods must be found in the employment of a scanning beam (ions or photons) directly interacting with the material to be removed, not enabling purely dielectric and metallic confinement to be achieved. An alternative approach is to use lithographic techniques based on laser-scanning methods to polymerize protective masks for subsequent processing. Methods based on linear optical properties (such as UV laser-scanning) [28] are not an option, since they require the deposition of thin films, and the fiber edge would not allow for spin coating at high rotations per minute (rpm) rate. In addition, the reflectance of the metal layer would imply a high reflection of the UV beam causing uncontrolled polymerization of resist in unintended locations (ghost spots), since the absorption of the resist would be linear with the power density. This is not the case for two-photon polymerization, where the dependence of the absorption is quadratic on the exposure power. Therefore, polymerization only takes place within a confined volume (voxel) allowing to process the fiber within a drop resist and with no ghost spots [29]. However, the approach in ref [29] only allows small-patterned areas, since it involves polymerizing a resist block followed by the deposition of the metallic layer via a 3-stage evaporation to leave uncovered the lateral walls of the resist block and facilitate mask removal. Following the removal of the cured resist, an optical window is obtained on the metal TF. However, this approach is not suitable when it is desired to obtain a wide dielectric region extended 360° around the optical fiber axis, which would allow to fully control the light-guiding properties of the implantable waveguide.

Here we propose an unconventional approach that relies on the exploitation of non-planar two-photon lithography at low numerical aperture (low-NA TPL) to pattern extended surfaces of tapered optical fibers all-around the implant axis. This method does not involve using a beam of light or ions interacting destructively with the metal and the dielectric surfaces, achieving alternating metal and dielectric confinement along conical regions without altering the refractive index or inducing roughness or doping of exposed silica surfaces. Overall, this approach enhances the engineering capabilities of light transmission and collection across mode splitting, as dielectric sections can be alternated with metal-confined regions with steep transitions at their interfaces. In particular, the nonplanar nature of the approach allows for an extended circular dielectric region along the taper, enabling a 360° efficient optical interfacing with the surrounding medium.

Results

Conformal patterning based on low NA two-photon lithography.

The fabrication method presented in this study exploits low-numerical aperture non-planar two-photon lithography to photo-polymerize a negative-tone photoresist mask along and around a metal-coated TF, aiming at the definition of large-area dielectric-confined waveguide sections alternated to metal-confined ones. We employed a low-NA objective (OLYMPUS XFLUOR 4X/340, NA=0.28) to focus a 785 nm femtosecond pulsed laser on the edge of the TF. The position of the focused beam was controlled by a three-

mirror galvanometric scan-head [30], with the TF mounted on a 4-axis piezoelectric stage to enable roto-translational movements while being submerged in a droplet of a photoresist (IP-S 780 Nanoscribe GmbH) casted in a polymeric container (**Figure 1A**). Compared to one-photon absorption, the non-linear nature of the two-photon process restricts the polymerization process to an ellipsoidal focal volume, (voxel). The voxel size is fundamentally influenced by Abbe's Law, and therefore it strongly depends on the NA of the objective lens and the wavelength of the laser beam [31]. In particular, the axial (d_z) and the in-plane (d_{xy}) voxel size scale differently as a function of NA. The voxel aspect ratio is given by the following relation [32]:

$$\frac{d_z}{d_{x,y}} \sim \frac{4}{NA} \quad (1)$$

where $d_z \sim \frac{2\lambda}{NA^2}$ and $d_{x,y} \sim \frac{\lambda}{2NA}$ [33]. Equation (1) is graphically reported in **Figure 1B(top)**, highlighting how for $NA < 0.4$ an in-plane voxel size of a few micrometers corresponds to a d_z in the order of several tens of μm . This is a crucial aspect in designing TPL processes on non-planar surfaces, since the voxel adhesion on the taper edge is ensured only under specific conditions related to the voxel dimensions and the curvature radius. Considering a pattern with transversal size W_{xy} and an axial voxel size d_z (ref. to **Figure 1B (bottom, left)**), the adhesion on the taper edge is possible until the voxel is in contact with the fiber surface, hence the maximum transversal width as a function of position along the fiber axis $W_x^{\max}(y)$ and axial voxel size is given by:

$$W_x^{\max}(y) = 2 \sqrt{R(y)^2 - \left(R(y) - \frac{d_z}{2}\right)^2} \quad (2)$$

Therefore, the circumference's arc (A) (**Figure 1A(bottom, right)**) that can be patterned without rotating the fiber depends on R

$$A = \frac{2\pi R(y) \cdot \alpha}{360^\circ} \quad (3)$$

For polymerizing a uniform resist mask, d_{xy} should be small enough to achieve high-resolution in the (x,y) plane to pattern also small curvature radii, while d_z should be high enough to enable the polymerization of thick resist masks to avoid time-consuming exposure of multiple layers (**Figure 1C**). Misalignment between exposures can indeed result in defects in the uniformity and consistency across different planes, compromising the subsequent wet etching steps. The system equipped with the 0.28NA objective offers a field of view FOV of $\approx 3 \text{ mm} \times 3 \text{ mm}$ and a polymerizing voxel with sizes $d_{xy} = 3 \mu m \pm 1 \mu m$ and $d_z = 32 \mu m \pm 5 \mu m$ [34]. This results in a polymerization time of $9,87 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ s}/\mu m^3$ (for a total of 80 s for a representative resist block of dimensions of $450 \times 60 \times 30 \mu m^3$ at a scanning speed of $200 \mu m/s$). The fabrication of a resist mask with the same dimensions with a higher NA objective would require polymerization at multiple focal planes in a much smaller FOV. By comparing the employed 0.28NA objective with a standard 1.05 NA OLYMPUS XLPLN 25XWMP2 (FOV $\approx 400 \mu \times 400 \mu m$, $d_{xy} =$

1.30 μm , $d_z = 5 \mu\text{m}$), patterning of the same volume takes longer time due to the smaller voxel size (more than 10 mn, a graphical comparison example is reported in **Figure 1C**).

Since we aim to fabricate TFs featuring alternating dielectric- and metallic-confined regions, we have employed the above-described approach to polymerize wide resist blocks around a metal-coated TF. After development, the representative output of the resist masks is reported in the processing flow displayed in **Figure 1D**, depicting the fabrication steps to obtain two 360° dielectric regions W1 and W2 on metal-coated TF. After TPL, the processed TF undergoes to wet-etching steps to uncover the underlying silica only in the non-masked sections of the taper. For this purpose, the TF is mounted on a motorized stage which controls the immersion in the etchant solution to stop before the second protective resist mask is totally immersed (**Supplementary Figure S1**). Finally, the resist is removed by soaking the fiber in $H_2SO_4:H_2O_2$ 3:1 solution and rinsing it in de-ionized H_2O , to uncover the underlying metallic layer. **Figure 1E** displays the patterned TF, equipped with two dielectric sections that establish 360° optical channels, whose extension along the fiber length can be tailored by tuning the dimensions of the polymerized resist mask. As can be noted by observing the final probe, the transition from metal waveguide to dielectric waveguide is sharp, the edges of the dielectric sections are continuous, and its surface is free of roughness. This makes a key difference with the same type of patterning realized through FIB milling: the milling is not continuous around the optical fiber axis but operated at steps of 90-degrees, therefore each milled region overlaps with the previous one (**Supplementary Figure S2**) resulting in stitching defects. In addition, to achieve the same dimensions of W2, FIB would require more than 30 hours of continuous milling, possibly inducing a non-uniform alteration of the refractive index, due to Ga ions implantation [25]. These drawbacks may reduce the emission and collection efficiency of the dielectric regions fabricated on the metallic fiber cladding, whose purpose is the site-selective light delivery and collection around the implant position [20].

These drawbacks are relevant since they impact the optical transmission efficiency. In the following, we will describe how the properties of the W1 and W2 regions are uninfluenced by the low-NA TPL process and by virtue of the surface homogeneity allow for symmetrical emission and collection, governed by modal multiplexing and demultiplexing properties of the patterned TF.

Figure 1 **A**) *top* Voxel Aspect Ratio as a function of NA. *bottom, left* Maximum polymerizable width of a resist block as a function of fiber radius and axial voxel size. *bottom, right* Maximum circumference that can be patterned without rotating the fiber depending on R. **B**) Schematic representation of the used custom system. The metal-coated TF is mounted on a 4-axis piezoelectric stage and submerged in a PDMS tank filled with a negative-tone photoresist. The laser beam is focused and scanned on the tapered surface through a low-NA objective lens. **C**) Comparison between the voxel dimension of low (bottom) and high (top) NA objective. **D**) Representation of the main fabrication step. **E**) TF at the end of the process, equipped with two 360° optical apertures, achieving sharp transition between metal and dielectric material (Scale bar 200 μm).

Optical properties of tapered fibers with hybrid metal dielectric surface

As described in the previous paragraph, the low NA-TPL processing technique enables the fabrication of a sharp transition between metal- and dielectric-confined sections. In both the metallic and dielectric waveguide sections, the increases of the transversal wavevector component of a given guided mode (indexed by $[l,m]$ in the linearly polarized formulation [35]) at the beginning of the taper is governed by the equation:

$$k_{t[l,m]}(y_1) \sim \frac{R(y_2)}{R(y_1)} k_{t[l,m]}(y_2), \quad (2)$$

where $k_{t[l,m]}(y_1)$ and $k_{t[l,m]}(y_2)$ are the transversal propagation constants of the l,m -th guided mode at the section of radius $R(y_1)$ and $R(y_2)$, respectively, with $R(y_2) > R(y_1)$ (ref. **Fig. 2A**).

However, mode propagation is subject to boundary conditions, expressed by the following limits[35][18]:

$$\begin{cases} k_{t[l,m]}(\gamma) < k_0 n = 2\pi n/\lambda & \text{for metallic confinement } (n = 1.43) \\ k_{t[l,m]}(\gamma) < k_0 NA & \text{for dielectric confinement } (NA = 0.39) \end{cases}$$

This means: (i) in the case of metal confinement, when $k_{t[l,m]}(\gamma) > k_0 n$ the mode becomes evanescent, while (ii) when $k_{t[l,m]}(\gamma) > k_0 NA$ in dielectric confinement the mode becomes radiative, and the waveguide can exchange optical energy with the environment (i.e. can both deliver and collect light).

To study these mode-division properties for the hybrid metal-dielectric TFs proposed in this work, the structured TF (**Figure 1E**) was immersed in a PBS:fluorescein solution and a 473 nm continuous laser beam was injected into the fiber with a variable input angle $0^\circ < \theta_{in} < 23^\circ$ (**Figure 2B**) (fiber $NA = 0.39$) to excite well-defined subsets of guided modes and investigate their outcoupling through W1 and W2 (W1 and W2 are about $150 \mu m$ long, separated by about $450 \mu m$ of metallic waveguide). Light outcoupled through the dielectric sections generates fluorescence in the solution, and the corresponding image was collected by a sCMOS camera. Light emission images as a function of θ_{in} with steps of 1° are reported in **Supplementary video V1**, while **Figure 2C** displays false-color fluorescence images for the two input angles that maximize light output from W1 and W2 ($\theta_{in} = 0^\circ$ and $\theta_{in} = 12^\circ$, respectively). Excitation light is selectively emitted from W1 for $0 < \theta_{in} < 6^\circ$ or from W2 for $9^\circ < \theta_{in} < 18^\circ$ (see emission profiles in **Figure D**). Very little light delivery was detected from W2 for angles activating W1 and from W1 for angles activating W2. To quantify this “cross-talk” between the apertures we evaluated the Extinction Ratio (ER) for each dielectric section, defined as the maximum counts of light intensity emitted from the active section, divided by the maximum counts emitted from the non-active one. We found $ER_{W1} > 65:1$ and $ER_{W2} > 20:1$, marking a substantial difference with respect to TFs realized through ion beam milling [23] or laser ablation methods [26], which can achieve lower ERs for much smaller patterns due to the induced changes on the properties of the dielectric waveguide. The hypothesis of the low influence of our low-NA npTPL process on the dielectric properties is further supported by **Supplementary Figure S3**, displaying sequential frames extracted from **Supplementary video V1** for $9^\circ < \theta_{in} < 17^\circ$. At $\theta_{in} = 9^\circ$ light is emitted mostly from the lower part of the dielectric section, and while θ_{in} increases light delivery moves to wider diameters. This phenomenon is evident as the fabrication protocol presented in this work allows for sufficiently extended dielectric regions that modal separation can be observed even within them as a direct consequence of mode-division demultiplexing being efficient within the dielectric section. This change of position is indeed accompanied at high input angles by an increase of light output angles ($\theta_{out} \sim 15^\circ$ at $\theta_{in} = 9^\circ$, while $\theta_{out} \sim 40^\circ$ at $\theta_{in} = 17^\circ$, reflecting also the increase of kt due to the propagation in the metal-confined region above W2 due to equation (2)).

Figure 2 **A)** TF equipped with two 360° dielectric regions W1 and W2. **B)** Angle-selective injective system. **C)** False-color fluorescence images at the two angles for which the output power density is maximum. **D)** **top** Emission profile for W1 and W2 at different input angles in the range $0^\circ \leq \theta_{in} \leq 23^\circ$. Red arrow points to the maximum emission profile from W1, while the yellow arrow points to the maximum emission profile from W2. **bottom** Maximum emission from W1 for $\theta_{in} = 0^\circ$ (red box) and from W2 for $\theta_{in} = 12^\circ$ (green box).

Collection properties characterization

The dielectric-guiding sections represent bi-directional optical interface channels, allowing for site-selective light delivery in deep brain regions as well as for the collection of functional fluorescence in a reconfigurable approach. To quantify the modal separation between collected light from W1 and W2, a far-field collection path was implemented coaxially to light injection to excite and collect fluorescence through W1 and W2 (**Figure 3A, left**), with the taper being submerged in a PBS:fluorescein (30 μM) solution. Fluorescence emitted close to the dielectric regions was collected back through the fiber and outcoupled on the bench-top optical setup. The far-field plane of the fiber facet was imaged on an sCMOS camera, detecting two well-distinct disk and annular patterns for $\theta_{in} = 0^\circ$ and $\theta_{in} = 12^\circ$, respectively (**Figure 3A, right**). The radius of the disk $\vec{R}(k_x, k_y)$ is directly related to the k_t of light re-emitted by the fiber facet through the relation[22]:

$$k_t = \frac{2\pi}{\lambda} \sin \left[\tan^{-1} \left(\frac{f_2}{f_2 f_3} |\vec{R}(k_x, k_y)| \right) \right]$$

Where f_1, f_2, f_3 are the focal lengths of lenses L1, L2 and L3, specified in the 3D setup sketch in **Figure 3A, left**. This results in a modal separation between W1 and W2, whose wavevectors are $K1 = 0.07 \pm 0.04$ and $K2 = 0.24 \pm 0.05$.

Together with the modal separation, an important figure of merit to define the light collection properties of the neural implant is the sensitive volume, which can be estimated by the *collection efficiency field* (η) [36]. With this aim, we employed the two-photon scanning system schematized in **Figure 3B, left**. The fiber was submerged in a PBS:fluorescein (30 μM) droplet and a fs-pulsed laser ($\lambda = 920$ nm) was used to generate

a point fluorescent source scanning close to W1 and W2 alternately, on the $\sim 1.4 \times 1.4 \text{ mm}^2$ FOV enabled by a 4X/0.28NA objective. The excited fluorescence is collected through the dielectric sections and sent to a photomultiplier tube (*f-PMT*). *f-PMT* is synchronized with the microscope scan head and allows to build a two-dimensional map $f(x, y)$ of collected fluorescence. The image $\mu(x, y)$ acquired through the non-descanned microscope PMT (*μ -PMT*) was also collected and used to quantify the uniformity of the microscope excitation in the FOV. The collection efficiency field was then calculated as the ratio $\eta(x, y) = f(x, y)/\mu(x, y)$, with a representative result displayed in **Figure 3B, right**.

η is then segmented into one image per dielectric section (η_{W1} and η_{W2}) and iso-intensity lines at 10%, 20%, 40%, 60%, 80% and 90% of the maximum number of collected counts are extracted (**Figure 3C**). By virtue of the highly-symmetric η_{W1} and η_{W2} the iso-intensity lines can be rotated by 180° around the fiber to estimate iso-intensity surfaces (**Figure 3C, center**). By following an analytical procedure, based on the Pappus-Guldin theorem we calculated the volume of rotational solids (described in **Supplementary Figure S4**). We have estimated the iso-volumes by multiplying the area enclosed by the iso-intensity lines by the distance between the barycenter of the iso-surfaces and the optical axis of the fiber, by the angle of rotation. The resulting volumes are reported in a bar diagram in **Figure 3C, right**. The volume described by the rotation of these surfaces reflects the regions from which a given fraction of collected photons arise. Consequently, it represents the effective volume from which functional signals can be detected [34]. The symmetry found in η_{W1} and η_{W2} , achieved through the advantages enjoyed by low-NA npTFL, is not reached by the alternative fabrication methods. For instance, as shown in **Figure 3D**, the inhomogeneity of the dielectric surface FIB milled leads to asymmetric light emission and thus asymmetry in the collection diagram.

To verify the ability of such probe to collect fluorescence from brain tissue, the hybrid metal-dielectric TF was inserted in fixed coronal brain slices from *Thy1-ChR2-YFP* mice, in such a way to have W2 positioned between layer III and layer IV of the somatosensory cortex, since the layer IV should be characterized by the expression of yellow fluorescence protein in the soma of pyramidal neurons[37]. This is showcased in **Figure 4A, left**, acquired through the *μ -PMT* while scanning a laser beam as for the case of the measurement in the PBS:fluorescein solution. Simultaneously, generated fluorescence was acquired through the dielectric sections and sent to *f-PMT*, enabling the estimation of the collection diagram of the device directly inserted into the relevant environment (**Figure 4A, center**). Upon merging the two images (**Figure 4A, right**), we observed that while fluorescence was generated across the entire FOV, only the fluorescence arising close to W1 and W2 was captured by the *f-PMT*. A qualitative estimation of the collected fluorescence intensity is represented in **Figure 4B**, displaying a bar graph of the number of counts for increasing levels of collected signal from W1 and W2 respectively. In addition, as shown in **Figure 4C**, and we **Figure 4D** are able to detect a discrete number of cell bodies in deep cortical layers, and for the considered dielectric aperture, we also estimated the distance within which optical signals of neural activity can be collected, finding it to be about $200 \mu\text{m}$ from the axis of the optical fiber.

Figure 3 **A)** *left* 3D sketch of the optical path employed for selective excitation and far-field collection. *right* Images detected by the sCMOS camera. **B)** *left* Schematic representation of the optical setup used to excite and collect functional fluorescence through the microscope PMT (μ detector) and the fiber PMT (f detector). *right* False-color image of the collection field (η) of W1 and W2. **C)** *left* The iso-intensity lines at 10%, 20%, 40%, 60%, 80% and 90% of the maximum number of collected counts from both apertures. *center* The cross-sectional views of the 3-dimensional reconstructions of the collection field for W1 (bottom) and W2 (top). *right*, Numerical estimation of the collection volumes. **D)** *top, left* 360° dielectric region milled via FIB. *top, right* Zoom in of milled dielectric region (scale bar 10 μm). *bottom* The iso-intensity lines at 20%, 30%, 40%, 60%, 80% and 90% of the maximum number of collected counts from the milled dielectric region.

Figure 4 **A) left** Image of TF, implanted in a fixed brain slice, acquired through the μ -PMT (scale bar 200 μm). **center** Image acquired through f-PMT of the excited fluorescence collected by W1 and W2 (scale bar 200 μm). **Right** Merge of the two images from f-PMT and μ -PMT. **B)** A qualitative estimation of the collected fluorescence intensity is displayed in a bar graph of the number of counts for increasing levels of collected signal from W1 and W2 respectively. **C)** 13x zoom of W2 implanted between layer III and layer IV, highlighting the ability to detect a discrete number of cell bodies up to 200 μm relative to the optical fiber axis, symmetrically from both sides of the dielectric region. **D)** Quantitative estimation of the cells number detected by W2 in the brain region accessible by the dielectric section.

Discussion and conclusion

In this manuscript, we propose low-NA TPL to achieve high-resolution patterning over large volumes around the optical axis of a metal-coated TF in extremely short fabrication times (<10 min including polymerization, developing, etching and removing of cured resist) compared to other techniques. In fact, the same type of patterning (W1 and W2 length $\sim 150\ \mu\text{m}$ extending around the fiber axis) would take 4 to 30 hours if fabricated with FIB milling and about 30 minutes with laser ablation but results in lower resolution. In addition, using lithography to obtain a waveguide with the alternation of dielectric and metallic confinement offers several additional advantages over other techniques, including: no alteration of original surface roughness, no modification of the silica refractive index, and no deformation in pattern edges due to localized heating.

The resulting hybrid metal-dielectric TFs, whose aim is to establish multiple optical bi-directional channels along the implant axis, not only enable selective light delivery but also demonstrate efficient optical collection with minimal cross-talk. As the refractive index and the roughness of the dielectric-confined sections were not compromised by the fabrication process, they showed a highly symmetrical collection efficiency field (η), which can be observed from the iso-intensity lines, allowing uniform and consistent optical interaction with the surrounding tissue. This is a significant improvement over devices fabricated by traditional methods, whose dielectric regions fail to achieve the same quality of 360° symmetric collection due to several factors that alter their optical and morphological properties. Tests in fixed coronal brain slices from *Thy1-ChR2-YFP* mice confirmed the ability to collect signals not only in a homogeneous medium, but also in the presence of strong scattering in the mouse cortical layers. The estimated effective collection volume extends up to about $200\ \mu\text{m}$ from the axis of the optical fiber, and the freedom in defining the patterning size and shapes can allow engineering the collection volume to target deep brain regions otherwise difficult to reach.

Material and methods

Device Fabrication

Metal-coated TFs, employed for the fabrication of the final devices equipped with optical apertures, were supplied by Optogenix starting from optical fibers with 0.39 numerical aperture and core/cladding diameter of $200/225\ \mu\text{m}$ respectively (ThorlabsFT200EMT). The tapered shape (active length $1100\ \mu\text{m}$ and taper angle of about 6°) was achieved by a heat-and-pull method following the procedure described in ref. [38]. The fiber was then subjected to e-beam evaporation of a 5 nm Chromium (Cr), to improve the adhesion of the gold layer, deposited by a second evaporation of 200 nm of Gold (Au). Using gold to cover the fiber surface allows to obtain, at the end of the fabrication process, a probe that is ready to be tested in vivo, without having to be encapsulated with an additional biocompatible material. After metal deposition, the fiber is mounted on a motor which allows to rotate the fibers around the motor axis for the entire duration of the evaporation, ensuring homogeneous deposition at a rate of approximately $1.0\ \text{\AA}/\text{s}$.

After depositing the metal layer, a TPL process was performed to polymerize resist masks along and around the taper axis, thanks to a custom setup described in ref. [30]. Briefly, the metal-coated TF is mounted on a 4-axis piezoelectric stage, which allows to move the fiber in the three spatial directions and to rotate it

around its optical axis. The taper region was immersed in a PDMS chamber filled with a negative tone photoresist (Nanoscribe IP-S 780) while a femtosecond pulsed laser, controlled by a pair of galvanometric mirrors, was focused on the fiber surface via a low NA 4X objective (OLYMPUS XFLUOR 4X/340).

The laser spot induces a polymerization reaction in a confined volume, called voxel, whose three dimensions are $d_{xy} = 3 \mu m$ and $d_z = 32 \mu m$. The large voxel size provides the possibility to polymerize thick resist masks (4 in total to cover the fiber surface at 360°) without changing the focal plane. Each mask was polymerized with a writing speed of $200 \mu m/s$ and power density at the focal plane of $4.36 TW/cm^2$. After removing the unpolymerized resist by submerging the fiber in the SU-8 developer solution, the fiber is mounted on a motorized motor to control the immersion in the etchant solutions. Indeed, the fiber must be dipped for a length not exceeding the second resist block (**Figure S1** in *Supplementary Materials*), so that the metal layer is removed only in the regions between the two resist masks.

The last step involves removing the cured resist by soaking the fiber in an $H_2SO_4:H_2O_2$ 3:1 solution and rinsing it in de-ionized H_2O thus obtaining a device with two all-dielectric 360° optical apertures. The number and size of these apertures can be modified by changing the number or size of the resist masks.

Light injection system

To study the emission properties of the probe, it is immersed in a drop of PBS: fluorescein solution ($30 \mu M$) and a selective injection system, sketched in **Figure 2B**, is used to couple the light into the fiber core. A 473 nm laser beam (Laser Quantum Ciel 473) is focused on a galvanometric system (GVS001 - 1D Galvo System, Silver-Coated Mirror) and directed towards the first lens L1 ($f_1 = 100$ mm, Thorlabs AL50100-A) with a θ_{GM} angle. The collimated beam from L1 passes through a second lens L2 ($f_1 = 32$ mm, Thorlabs AL4532-A) and enters into a patch cord with an input angle (θ_{in}) depending on θ_{GM} . The patch cord is connected to TF with a ferrule-to-ferrule junction and based on θ_{in} , light is outcoupled from W1 or W2. The light generates fluorescence in the solution, while the corresponding image is collected by a sCMOS camera.

Far-field detection system

After the emission through the light injection system, the fluorescence excited close to the optical apertures is collected by the dielectric region of the probe and guided via a patch cord to the far-field detection path **Figure 3A, left**. The collected light passes through the lens L1 (ThorLabs LA4532-A, $f_1 = 32$ mm) and is focused on the back focal plane of L1. The other two lenses L2 (ThorLabs LA1301, $f_2 = 250$ mm) and L3 (ThorLabs LA1050-N-BK7, $f_3 = 100$ mm) are needed to enlarge the far-field pattern to match the size of the chip of the scientific Complementary Metal–Oxide Semiconductor (sCMOS) camera (Hamamatsu C11440 Orca Flash 4.0). Before reaching the camera sensor, the light is filtered by an NIR filter and a bandpass filter (BPF) to exclusively detect light within the wavelength range of 500–550 nm.

Collection characterization system

A two-photon laser scanning system (**Figure 3B, left**), described in detail by *Pisanello M. et al.* [34] and *Montinaro et al.* [39], is used to characterize the collection properties of the probe in both a semi-transparent solution (PBS: fluorescein 30 μ M) and fixed brain slices (*Thy1-ChR2-YFP*). In the case of light collection in tissue, the fiber is inserted into the brain slice by using a micromanipulator, while live monitoring the image with a sCMOS camera. A 920 nm fs-pulsed laser beam (Coherent Chameleon Discovery) is scanned in the (x,y) plane, close to W1 and W2, by a galvo/galvo head and focused on the sample by employing an objective lens (Olympus XLFLUOR-340 4x/NA 0.28). The generated fluorescence light is collected via the same objective and reflected, by using a dichroic mirror (Semrock FF665-Di02), toward a non-descanned photomultiplier tube, which we call microscope PMT (Hamamatsu H10770PA-40). Simultaneously, part of the fluorescence is detected by the optical apertures of the fiber, butt-coupled to a patch cord. The fluorescent light back-emitted from the patch cord is collected by a microscope objective (Olympus Plan N 40x) and is guided to a second PMT (fiber PMT, Hamamatsu H7422P-40), through two spherical lenses (Thorlabs LA1050-A and LA1805-A) and a band-pass filter (Semrock FF03-525/50-25).

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Conflict of interest

M.D.V. and Fe.P. are founders and hold private equity in Optogenix, a company that develops, produces, and sells technologies to deliver light into the brain.

References

- [1] B. J. Barros and J. P. S. Cunha, "Neurophotonics: a comprehensive review, current challenges and future trends," *Front Neurosci*, vol. 18, May 2024, doi: 10.3389/fnins.2024.1382341.
- [2] M. Brondi, M. Bruzzone, C. Lodovichi, and M. dal Maschio, "Optogenetic Methods to Investigate Brain Alterations in Preclinical Models," *Cells*, vol. 11, no. 11, p. 1848, Jun. 2022, doi: 10.3390/cells11111848.
- [3] O. Yizhar, L. E. Fenno, T. J. Davidson, M. Mogri, and K. Deisseroth, "Optogenetics in Neural Systems," *Neuron*, vol. 71, no. 1, pp. 9–34, Jul. 2011, doi: 10.1016/j.neuron.2011.06.004.
- [4] N. J. Sofroniew, D. Flickinger, J. King, and K. Svoboda, "A large field of view two-photon mesoscope with subcellular resolution for in vivo imaging," *Elife*, vol. 5, Jun. 2016, doi: 10.7554/eLife.14472.
- [5] A. Balena, M. Bianco, F. Pisanello, and M. De Vittorio, "Recent Advances on High-Speed and Holographic Two-Photon Direct Laser Writing," *Adv Funct Mater*, p. 2211773, Feb. 2023, doi: 10.1002/adfm.202211773.
- [6] X. Cheng, S. Sadegh, S. Zilpelwar, A. Devor, L. Tian, and D. A. Boas, "Comparing the fundamental imaging depth limit of two-photon, three-photon, and non-degenerate two-photon microscopy," *Opt Lett*, vol. 45, no. 10, p. 2934, May 2020, doi: 10.1364/OL.392724.
- [7] A. Abdelfattah *et al.*, "Neurophotonic Tools for Microscopic Measurements and Manipulation: Status Report," *Neurophotonics*, vol. 9, no. S1, Apr. 2022, doi: 10.1117/1.NPh.9.S1.013001.
- [8] F. Der Chen *et al.*, "Implantable nanophotonic neural probes for integrated patterned photostimulation and electrophysiology recording," *bioRxiv*, p. 2023.11.14.567101, Jan. 2023, doi: 10.1101/2023.11.14.567101.
- [9] A. Mohanty *et al.*, "Reconfigurable nanophotonic silicon probes for sub-millisecond deep-brain optical stimulation," *Nat Biomed Eng*, vol. 4, no. 2, pp. 223–231, Feb. 2020, doi: 10.1038/s41551-020-0516-y.
- [10] W. D. Sacher *et al.*, "Visible-light silicon nitride waveguide devices and implantable neurophotonic probes on thinned 200 mm silicon wafers," *Opt Express*, vol. 27, no. 26, p. 37400, Dec. 2019, doi: 10.1364/OE.27.037400.
- [11] L. Lu *et al.*, "Wireless optoelectronic photometers for monitoring neuronal dynamics in the deep brain," *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, vol. 115, no. 7, Feb. 2018, doi: 10.1073/pnas.1718721115.
- [12] Z. C. Zhou *et al.*, "Deep-brain optical recording of neural dynamics during behavior," *Neuron*, vol. 111, no. 23, pp. 3716–3738, Dec. 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.neuron.2023.09.006.

- [13] S. Il Park *et al.*, "Soft, stretchable, fully implantable miniaturized optoelectronic systems for wireless optogenetics," *Nat Biotechnol*, vol. 33, no. 12, pp. 1280–1286, Dec. 2015, doi: 10.1038/nbt.3415.
- [14] S. Park, G. Loke, Y. Fink, and P. Anikeeva, "Flexible fiber-based optoelectronics for neural interfaces," *Chem Soc Rev*, vol. 48, no. 6, pp. 1826–1852, 2019, doi: 10.1039/C8CS00710A.
- [15] M. Bianco *et al.*, "Comparative study of autofluorescence in flat and tapered optical fibers towards application in depth-resolved fluorescence lifetime photometry in brain tissue," *Biomed Opt Express*, vol. 12, no. 2, p. 993, Feb. 2021, doi: 10.1364/BOE.410244.
- [16] B. M. Silveira *et al.*, "Side-view holographic endomicroscopy via a custom-terminated multimode fibre," *Opt Express*, vol. 29, no. 15, p. 23083, Jul. 2021, doi: 10.1364/OE.426235.
- [17] F. Pisanello *et al.*, "Multipoint-Emitting Optical Fibers for Spatially Addressable In Vivo Optogenetics," *Neuron*, vol. 82, no. 6, pp. 1245–1254, Jun. 2014, doi: 10.1016/j.neuron.2014.04.041.
- [18] M. Pisanello, A. Della Patria, L. Sileo, B. L. Sabatini, M. De Vittorio, and F. Pisanello, "Modal demultiplexing properties of tapered and nanostructured optical fibers for in vivo optogenetic control of neural activity," *Biomed Opt Express*, vol. 6, no. 10, p. 4014, Oct. 2015, doi: 10.1364/BOE.6.004014.
- [19] F. Pisanello *et al.*, "Dynamic illumination of spatially restricted or large brain volumes via a single tapered optical fiber," *Nat Neurosci*, vol. 20, no. 8, pp. 1180–1188, Aug. 2017, doi: 10.1038/nn.4591.
- [20] M. Pisanello *et al.*, "Tailoring light delivery for optogenetics by modal demultiplexing in tapered optical fibers," *Sci Rep*, vol. 8, no. 1, p. 4467, Mar. 2018, doi: 10.1038/s41598-018-22790-z.
- [21] F. Pisano *et al.*, "Depth-resolved fiber photometry with a single tapered optical fiber implant," *Nat Methods*, vol. 16, no. 11, pp. 1185–1192, Nov. 2019, doi: 10.1038/s41592-019-0581-x.
- [22] M. Bianco *et al.*, "Orthogonalization of far-field detection in tapered optical fibers for depth-selective fiber photometry in brain tissue," *APL Photonics*, vol. 7, no. 2, Feb. 2022, doi: 10.1063/5.0073594.
- [23] F. Pisano *et al.*, "Focused ion beam nanomachining of tapered optical fibers for patterned light delivery," *Microelectron Eng*, vol. 195, pp. 41–49, Aug. 2018, doi: 10.1016/j.mee.2018.03.023.
- [24] A. Micco, A. Ricciardi, M. Pisco, V. La Ferrara, and A. Cusano, "Optical fiber tip templating using direct focused ion beam milling," *Sci Rep*, vol. 5, no. 1, p. 15935, Nov. 2015, doi: 10.1038/srep15935.
- [25] F. S. Jamaludin, M. F. Mohd Sabri, and S. M. Said, "Controlling parameters of focused ion beam (FIB) on high aspect ratio micro holes milling," *Microsystem Technologies*, vol. 19, no. 12, pp. 1873–1888, Dec. 2013, doi: 10.1007/s00542-013-1912-y.

- [26] A. Rizzo *et al.*, "Laser micromachining of tapered optical fibers for spatially selective control of neural activity," *Microelectron Eng*, vol. 192, pp. 88–95, May 2018, doi: 10.1016/j.mee.2018.02.010.
- [27] A. Balena *et al.*, "Two-photon fluorescence-assisted laser ablation of non-planar metal surfaces: fabrication of optical apertures on tapered fibers for optical neural interfaces," *Opt Express*, vol. 28, no. 15, p. 21368, Jul. 2020, doi: 10.1364/OE.395187.
- [28] H. S. Kim, B. H. Son, Y. C. Kim, and Y. H. Ahn, "Direct laser writing lithography using a negative-tone electron-beam resist," *Opt Mater Express*, vol. 10, no. 11, p. 2813, Nov. 2020, doi: 10.1364/OME.409302.
- [29] B. Spagnolo *et al.*, "Tapered fiberoptodes for optoelectrical neural interfacing in small brain volumes with reduced artefacts," *Nat Mater*, vol. 21, no. 7, pp. 826–835, Jul. 2022, doi: 10.1038/s41563-022-01272-8.
- [30] M. Pisanello, D. Zheng, A. Balena, F. Pisano, M. De Vittorio, and F. Pisanello, "An open source three-mirror laser scanning holographic two-photon lithography system," *PLoS One*, vol. 17, no. 4, p. e0265678, Apr. 2022, doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0265678.
- [31] Z. Faraji Rad, P. D. Prewett, and G. J. Davies, "High-resolution two-photon polymerization: the most versatile technique for the fabrication of microneedle arrays," *Microsyst Nanoeng*, vol. 7, no. 1, p. 71, Sep. 2021, doi: 10.1038/s41378-021-00298-3.
- [32] V. Harinarayana and Y. C. Shin, "Two-photon lithography for three-dimensional fabrication in micro/nanoscale regime: A comprehensive review," *Opt Laser Technol*, vol. 142, p. 107180, Oct. 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.optlastec.2021.107180.
- [33] J. Fischer and M. Wegener, "Three-dimensional optical laser lithography beyond the diffraction limit," *Laser Photon Rev*, vol. 7, no. 1, pp. 22–44, Jan. 2013, doi: 10.1002/lpor.201100046.
- [34] M. Pisanello *et al.*, "The Three-Dimensional Signal Collection Field for Fiber Photometry in Brain Tissue," *Front Neurosci*, vol. 13, Feb. 2019, doi: 10.3389/fnins.2019.00082.
- [35] L. J. D. Snyder A. W., *Optical Waveguide Theory*, Springer. 1983.
- [36] M. Pisanello *et al.*, "The Three-Dimensional Signal Collection Field for Fiber Photometry in Brain Tissue," *Front Neurosci*, vol. 13, Feb. 2019, doi: 10.3389/fnins.2019.00082.
- [37] N. Huidobro, A. Mendez-Fernandez, I. Mendez-Balbuena, R. Gutierrez, R. Kristeva, and E. Manjarrez, "Brownian Optogenetic-Noise-Photostimulation on the Brain Amplifies Somatosensory-Evoked Field Potentials," *Front Neurosci*, vol. 11, Aug. 2017, doi: 10.3389/fnins.2017.00464.
- [38] L. Sileo, M. Pisanello, M. De Vittorio, and F. Pisanello, "Fabrication of multipoint light emitting optical fibers for optogenetics," H. Hirschberg, S. J. Madsen, E. D. Jansen, Q. Luo, S. K. Mohanty, and N. V. Thakor, Eds., Mar. 2015, p. 930520. doi: 10.1117/12.2075819.

- [39] C. Montinaro *et al.*, "Influence of the anatomical features of different brain regions on the spatial localization of fiber photometry signals," *Biomed Opt Express*, vol. 12, no. 10, p. 6081, Oct. 2021, doi: 10.1364/BOE.439848.